

THE APPLICATION OF RELIABILITY BASED OPTIMIZATION OF TOPHAT STIFFENED COMPOSITE PANELS UNDER BIDIRECTIONAL BUCKLING LOAD

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Abstract

A reliability based optimization method for minimization the weight of tophat stiffened composite panels with probabilistic deflection constraints is presented in this paper. An energy based grillage method is developed for the investigation of buckling problems under bidirectional in-plane loads. The variables that have large impact on structural safety have been identified, which will allow the optimization process be more quantitative and efficient. Parametric study of plate dimension and loading ratio is conducted to investigate the coupling effect on critical buckling load.

Keywords: Tophat-stiffened, Reliability based optimization, Grillage, Bidirectional load

Nomenclature

L Length of stiffened panel
 B Width of stiffened panel
 θ Plate aspect ratio
 I_g Moment of inertia of girder
 I_b Moment of inertia of beam
 N_g Number of longitudinal girders
 N_b Number of transverse beams
 N_x Uniform load in x direction
 N_y Uniform load in y direction
 α In-plane loading ratio
 w Deflection of plate

V_g Elastic strain energy of the girders

V_b Elastic strain energy of the beams

W The work done due to external load

1 Introduction

Composite materials have been increasingly used in aircraft, space and marine due to their outstanding strength, stiffness and light-weight properties [1]. In the construction of marine vessels, stiffened panels comprised of a plate, longitudinal stiffeners and transverse frame are the most commonly used structural elements, forming the deck, side shells and bulkheads. The composite structural behavior exhibits wide scatter as a result of the inherent uncertainties in manufacture and design variables. Structural reliability methods allow the engineers to reduce the probability of failure and lead to a balanced design. The reliability-based design optimization tries to find a highly reliable design by ensuring the satisfaction of probabilistic constraints, which is more flexible and consistent than corresponding deterministic analysis because they provide more rational safety levels over various types of structures and take into account more information that is not considered properly by deterministic analysis. Once the probabilistic model is established, probabilistic analysis is run and then the sensitivity factors are obtained in order to determine the importance of a random variable, which will allow the optimization process be more quantitative and efficient.

2 Analytical model

2.1 General configuration

The definition of a stiffened panel is a panel of plating bounded by, for example, transverse bulkheads, longitudinal bulkheads, side shell or large longitudinal girders [2]. A typical stiffened panel configuration with the tophat-section stiffeners is shown in Fig. 1. The stiffened panel is referred to x- and y- axis coinciding with its longitudinal and transverse edges, respectively, and a z-axis normal to its surface. The length and width of the stiffened panel are denoted by L and B , respectively. The spacing of the stiffeners is denoted by a between longitudinal stiffeners and b between transverse stiffeners. The numbers of longitudinal and transverse stiffeners are N_g and N_s , respectively. The web, table, and flange structures forming a tophat-stiffener are made of FRP laminates and they are assumed to be orthotropic plates.

Fig.1 Tophat stiffened panel configuration

2.2 Analytical analysis

The analysis of the stiffened composite panel is carried out based on grillage model developed by Vedeler [3]. The plate is compressed by in-plane load resultant of N_x and N_y in x and y direction respectively. The deflection, $w(x, y)$, at any point of the grillage is expressed by the following double summation of trigonometric series to Navier's energy method [4]:

$$w(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{B} \quad (1)$$

where m and n represent half-range sine expansions in x and y directions, respectively. The analysis of a grillage based methods are capable of giving comprehensive and adequate results. The potential energy, V , in a deflected grillage can be written as

$$V = V_g + V_b - W \quad (2)$$

V_g and V_b are the strain energies in the girders and beams respectively, which can be represented as [5],

$$V_g = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{N_g} E_{gi} I_{gi} \int_0^L \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)_{y=\frac{iB}{N_g+1}}^2 dx \quad (3)$$

$$V_b = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{N_b} E_{bj} I_{bj} \int_0^B \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right)_{x=\frac{jL}{N_b+1}}^2 dy \quad (4)$$

The work done W due to the bidirectional in-plane load, N_x and N_y , can be written as

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{N_g} \int_0^L N_x \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)_{y=\frac{iB}{N_g+1}}^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{N_b} \int_0^B N_y \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)_{x=\frac{jL}{N_b+1}}^2 dy \quad (5)$$

By using the energy method in structural analysis that maximum buckling load ($N_x = N_c$, $N_y = \alpha N_c$) often is approximated using energy conservation

$$V_g + V_b - W = 0 \quad (6)$$

Substitute Eq. 3, Eq. 4 and Eq. 5 into Eq. 6, the numerical critical buckling load can be obtained

$$N_c = \frac{\pi^2 \left[m^4 D_g (N_g + 1) + \theta^3 n^4 D_b (N_b + 1) \right]}{L^2 \left[m^2 (N_g + 1) + \alpha \theta n^2 (N_b + 1) \right]} \quad (7)$$

where $\theta = L/B$ and $\alpha = N_y/N_x$ are the plate aspect ratio and the in-plane loading ratio, respectively;

$D_g = \sum_{i=1}^{N_g} E_{gi} I_{gi}$ and $D_b = \sum_{j=1}^{N_b} E_{bj} I_{bj}$ are the flexural rigidity of the girder and beam, respectively.

3 Reliability based optimization

3.1 Optimization problem formulation

The design optimization problem considered in this research is that of the weight minimization of the tophat stiffened plate presented in Fig. 1. The RBO problem can be described mathematically as a search for the optimum values of design variables that would minimize panel weight subject to constraints on reliability and stress, and is formulated as

$$\begin{cases} \min & J \\ \text{s.t.} & \begin{cases} \lambda \geq 1 \\ \beta_d \leq \beta_{\min} \\ v_i^l \leq v_i \leq v_i^u \end{cases} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Those expressions show the objective function J with structural weight; λ is the buckling load ratio against the reference load; β_d is the calculated reliability index in the stiffened panel; β_{\min} is the minimum acceptable reliability index; v_i^l and v_i^u are the lower and upper bounds of the design variables, respectively. The total weight of the structure is calculated simply from the dimensions of the stiffened panel:

$$J = \left\{ \left(N_g L + N_b B \right) \left[\frac{LBt_1 + b_3 t_2 + 2b_f t_f}{t_3 \sqrt{(b_2 - b_3)^2 + 4d^2}} \right] \right\} \rho \quad (9)$$

The stiffener design variables are as follows: the stiffener height is d ; the crown width is b_3 ; the hat's lower end width is b_2 ; the total width of the tophat stiffener is b_1 ; the span a and b between transverse and longitudinal frames; and the number of stiffener plies is N_s . For the panel, the number of plies of the composite panel N_p and the dimension B and L are the design variables.

3.2 Optimization procedure

Based the computational framework [6], an integrated optimization procedure using a sequential linear programming scheme is developed to manage the interactions between optimization directed probabilistic and finite element (FE) responses. The flowchart of the general optimization procedure is given in Fig. 2.

1. *Design Variables Initialization*: The design variables (DVs) have the initial values set by the analyst at the start of the first optimization cycle. The values were allowed to be incremented up to 10 percent of their previous values in the subsequent cycles.

2. *FEA Solver*: A structural analysis Based FE model is performed and the nodal deflections and stress are calculated. The maximum nodal deflections and critical buckling load, needed for the reliability analysis as well as the constraint calculations, are extracted from the FEA output file and recorded.

3. *Design sensitivity Analysis (DSA) Solver*: A gradient based DSA was implemented for the evaluation of the sensitivity of the objective function with respect to the DVs. The importance that each random DV has on the overall panel response can be examined by the evaluation of sensitivity index, α .

4. *Model Uncertainty Evaluation*: In a reliability design method, each random variable is defined by the mean value, coefficient of variance (COV) and distribution type. The mean value together with the specified coefficients of variation COV, the corresponding standard deviations are calculated, and then passed as input to the structural reliability analysis (SRA).

5. *SRA implementation*: The reliability index of the structure is calculated based on the formulation of the statistical data on all random variables and the limit state function for deflection. For these calculations, a forward finite-difference scheme for numerical approximation of the required derivatives is used, which in turn requires a new FEA solution for each random variable perturbation. In the end, the resulting reliability index is passed on for the evaluation of reliability constraint.

6. *Evaluate design constraints*: The deflection constraint corresponding reliability index and buckling failure mode are evaluated, and checked for design feasibility as the objective function is minimized. The derivatives of all active and violated constraints, in addition to those of the objective function, are evaluated using a finite difference scheme in the gradient based optimization procedure.

7. *Convergence checking*: The optimum solution is found when changes in objective function are less

than $10e-3$. Otherwise, return to Step 1 until convergence is reached.

Fig.2 Flow chart of the optimization procedure

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Sensitivity analysis

The reliability of a structure is defined as the probability that the structure will perform its intended function without failing. Defining a performance function, $g(x)$, as the difference between structural “capacity” and “demand”, then the failure probability, p_f , is defined as

$$p_f = p[g(x) < 0] \quad (10)$$

In engineering practice, when g has a Normal distribution, the safety index, β , has a one to one correspondence with p_f , given by

$$\beta = -\Phi^{-1}(1 - p_f) \quad (11)$$

Sensitivity factor \mathcal{G} is generally considered as a measure of the sensitivity of the reliability index β with respect to the standard normal variable u_i . It provides some insight into the relative weight that

each one has in determining the final reliability of the structures [7].

$$\mathcal{G}_i = \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial u_i} \Big|_{u^*} = \frac{\mu_i}{\beta} \quad (12)$$

The deflection limit state function is defined as a function of the random variables,

$$g(x) = kw_{\max} - w(X_g, X_m, X_l) \quad (13)$$

where w_{\max} is the maximum displacement using the mean values of the design parameters; k is the safety factor; X_g, X_m, X_l represent the geometry, material and loading properties. All these variables are assumed as independent variables and they are randomly generated according to their assumed probability distribution as shown in Tab. 1.

Tab.1 Statics for random variable

Symbol	Mean value	C.O.V %	Distribution
L	3810	3	Normal
B	3810	3	Normal
t_1	12.7	3	Normal
b_2	108	3	Normal
b_3	92	3	Normal
b_f	54	3	Normal
t_2	8.6	3	Normal
t_3	4.0	3	Normal
d	132	3	Normal
E_f	826GPa	5	Normal
E_m	3.0GPa	5	Normal
G_f	413 GPa	5	Normal
G_m	1.09GPa	5	Normal
V_f	0.6	5	Normal
N_x	$0.5N_c$	15	Weibull
N_y	$0.5\alpha N_c$	15	Weibull
k	1.0	10	Normal

The dominant variables in the limit state equation on the reliability of the composite stiffened panel can be seen in Fig. 3. It can be observed that the importance of the dominant variables, by order, is the safety factor k , in-plane load N_x and N_y , plate dimension L and B , fibre volume V_f , and so forth. Other variables that play small roles in contributing to the probability of failure can be replaced by deterministic values in the structural optimization procedure.

Fig.3 Sensitivity factors of dominant variables

4.2 Finite element analysis

Maximum deflection and critical buckling load of a tophat stiffened composite panel subjected to bidirectional in-plane loads is carried out using the commercially available finite element program ANSYS 12.0, in which the shell element SHELL181 is used with a mesh density set to provide an element aspect ratio close to 1.0. The load ratio α against plate dimension ratio for a range of 0, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 is considered and the comparison is summarized in Tab. 2.

Tab.2 The comparison of critical buckling load with different load ratio and different plate aspect ratio

Dimension ratio, θ	Load ratio, α	Critical load, N_c
0.5	0	0.51051E+06
	0.5	0.16790E+07
	0.75	0.10946E+07
	1	0.45829E+06
	1.5	0.36503E+06
	2.0	0.30065E+06
1.0	0	0.64160E+06
	0.5	0.65332E+06
	0.75	0.62142E+06
	1	0.53673E+06
	1.5	0.41119E+06
	2.0	0.31124E+06
1.5	0	0.11074E+07
	0.5	0.10100E+07
	1.0	0.72720E+06
	1.5	0.54135E+06
	2.0	0.43719E+06
2.0	0	0.15214E+07

2.0	0.5	0.15215E+07
	1	0.12332E+07
	1.5	0.90698E+06
	2.0	0.70613E+06

4.3 Parametric study

Reliability based method shows that not only the mean value but also COV play a significant role in the procedure of structural optimization. Therefore, it is necessary to study the effects of the statistical distribution of the dominant variables with larger sensitivity factors. The results are computed by varying each of the parameters in turn with other variables held the same as previous analysis. Fig. 4 shows the result of the safety factor of the deflection limit state function k , the x directional load N_x , and the fiber volume V_f . It is evident that the reliability indices are strongly dependent on the variation of V_f . The safety factor of k and the x -directional load N_x are also very sensitive to the statistics of variables. Thus it will induce more meaningful results in the optimization procedure if more precisely knowing the statistics of these variables.

Fig.4 Influence of COV of k , N_x , V_f on reliability, β

The effects of plate aspect ratio and in-plane load ratio on the critical buckling load are investigated separately. Fig. 5 describes how the plate aspect ratio, θ , contributes to the optimum buckling load at a prescribed load ratio, α . It can be observed that θ has different effects on the buckling load for different values of α . In the case of $\alpha \geq 1$, the value of N_c increases when $\theta < 2$; In the case of

$\alpha < 1$, the value of N_c decreases dramatically when $\theta < 1$, and increases when $1 < \theta < 2$. However, in both cases above, the value of N_c remains almost unchanged for different values of θ . It is because N_y plays a dominant role for the buckling failure when $\alpha < 1$; while N_x becomes the dominant factor for the buckling failure mode when $\alpha \geq 1$. Fig. 6 describes how the in-plane load ratio contributes to the optimum buckling load at a prescribed plate aspect ratio. It can be observed that the effect is quite different between $\theta = 0.5$ and other cases. This is due to the changes in the buckling mode shape because of the stiffeners geometry and rigidity.

Fig.5 Optimum buckling load with aspect ratio, θ

Fig.6 Optimum buckling load with load ratio, α

5 Conclusions

A Reliability based optimization procedure is developed and applied to minimize the weight of tophat stiffened composite panels with probabilistic deflection constraints. An energy based grillage analytical method is successfully developed for the investigation of buckling problems under bidirectional in-plane loads. Reliability analysis has been performed on the structure, providing reliability indices and corresponding probabilities of failure can therefore be determined. The sensitivity results show that the model uncertainty and applied loads are very sensitive to the statics of variables. It can be observed from the parametric study that the plate aspect ratio and in-plane loading ratio have coupling effects on the critical buckling load. In the future it will be important to incorporate reliability within the failure criteria and take the in-plane loading ratio together with the plate dimension into consideration in the structure design procedure.

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